

CS TRACK
Investigating Citizen Science

Horizon 2020 / Science with and for Society Programme
Grant agreement number: 872522

Backup of the website, Community Platform and eMagazine

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 872522

This document provides access to the backup of the Community Platform and the eMagazine, both the files and the database, so that the installation can be restored on any server.

This is part of the sustainability and content preservation policy established in the CS Track project (reference: European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 872522), as indicated in deliverable D5.3 "Maintenance and Legacy for Community Platform".

For the specific technical indications, it is recommended to review section 3 "Maintenance and documentation to back-up practices and data policy" of deliverable D5.3, where the technical characteristics of the website and the management and administration system are indicated.

The website is built with WordPress 6.0 including a set of plugins that are all integrated into the installation.

The database is in MySQL with the standard WordPress format, the link to download files is the following: <http://cstrackbackup.ciberimaginario.es/>